

D5.7: Annual State of the Union Report – Part 3

How can ESF+ be optimised for social innovation?

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Grant Agreement No.: 693883
Project title: Social Innovation Community
Project acronym: SIC

Work package	WP5 - Policy	
Task	D5.7: Annual State of the Union Report – Part 3	
Originally submitted	20/12/2018	
Deliverable lead	Young Foundation/ Nesta	
Dissemination level	Public	
Nature	Report	
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Status	-	Plan
	-	Draft
	-	Working
	-	Final
	X	Submitted
	-	Approved

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Vitor Nogueira (DG EMPL), Costanza Pagini (Fondazione Giacomo Brodolini) and Marija Babovic (European Anti Poverty Network), and Gerhard Braunling (independent policy expert) who, in addition to partners in the SIC consortium, kindly offered invaluable feedback and comments on our key findings and recommendations. We are very grateful to all the interviewees and experts who participated in our research and policy roundtable discussions; they are listed in the annex to this report. We also extend our thanks to Isaac Stanley (Nesta) and Sandra Gulyurtlu (the Young Foundation), for their research support.

Disclaimer

This report is funded under the EC H2020 project SIC, Grant Agreement 693883. The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the SIC project consortium under EC grant agreement 693883 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

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Executive Summary

Since 2008, Europe's renewed Social Agenda has explored how the European social model can be made more modern, inclusive, innovative and sustainable.¹ The European Social Fund is arguably the EU's most powerful policy tool for creating a more 'social Europe'. As EU policymakers debate the future of ESF, this report asks: how can it be optimised for social innovation as a way to achieve these goals?

To create a 'social Europe', we need social innovation

Set up in 1957, the European Social Fund is the EU's primary instrument to invest in people. Among other things, it is now positioned as a key tool to deliver the commitments in the European Pillar of Social Rights (which was proclaimed late in 2017 by the European Parliament, the Council and the European Commission).

To be effective in doing this, it is imperative that the ESF can support innovative activities. Social innovation is needed to find the better ways to take forward the social legacies of European welfare states and combine them with institutions, relations and services that increase population wellbeing and enable social inclusion across the EU. Public authorities need to improve policies over time, creating systems that can adapt to changing needs. For example, digitalisation is changing the world of work, and employment and skills provision needs to adapt to help people prepare and re-skill. Meanwhile, social challenges and needs sometimes change quickly. The migrant crisis, for example, emerged in the middle of the EU's current programming period. As well as adapting for the long term, public authorities also need to be able to respond to new demands and needs as they emerge.

The ESF is potentially a powerful tool to enable public authorities to test and evaluate new approaches, take risks and involve citizens and communities in shaping public employment and skills services and solutions that combat social exclusion, poverty and discrimination, so that they are more effective and fit for purpose.

In recognition of this, the ESF explicitly makes provision for social innovation. Article 9 of the [ESF Regulation 2013](#) states that 'the ESF shall promote social innovation within all areas falling under its scope'. The ESF has, in fact, been a significant funder of social innovation during the 2014-2020 programming period. As of the end of 2017, **€2.84bn** has been allocated to social innovation as a

¹ European Commission (2010). What social Europe can do for you. Available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=4983&langId=en> [Accessed: 18/12/18]

'secondary theme'.²

However, social innovation activity appears to be concentrated in a relatively small number of places. Some 74% of ESF allocated to the social innovation secondary theme comes from just six countries: Germany, Portugal, Poland, Estonia, Austria and Italy.

In addition, our research suggests that there are several practical difficulties in using ESF for social innovation. Even when OPs allocate money to social innovation, they seem to have trouble spending it. Challenges with implementing social innovation within ESF are not surprising: a recent study found that the 'implementation of social innovation projects often clash with [ESF] rules and administrative systems that were designed for 'traditional' vocational training actions.'³ Compounding this further, our consultation found that while ESF managing bodies are tasked with designing social innovation project calls and support mechanisms, they often lack the expertise needed to do this effectively.⁴

Our qualitative research and synthesis of other relevant literature highlights several practical reasons why countries appear to have problems using ESF to fund social innovation:

- Member States and regional authorities seem to lack awareness about what social innovation is and what the benefits of supporting it are. In turn, this contributes to a lack of coordination, buy-in and support at key levels. This can contribute to wider cultural resistance to supporting social innovation through the ESF and lead to negative perceptions that such projects are riskier and require more effort.
- Inadequate institutional support for social experimentation results in a failure to sustain innovative solutions beyond project periods, and means that not enough is done to ensure that there are clear pathways for bottom-up innovations to eventually scale transnationally. Our consultations suggest that programme stakeholders have ad hoc guidance and support needs that the PROGRESS axis model of support for funding projects simply does not meet.
- Managing authorities are often not able, or not incentivised, to create effective partnerships, coordinate between different agencies, or lead actions that involve multiple stakeholders. For example, a survey carried out by Social Platform found that most managing authorities had not involved civil society as a partner in the design and implementation of funding – even though they are obliged to do so.⁵

² This figure is based on our own analysis of ESF spend data up to the end of 2017. In the report cited earlier, Fondazione Giacomo Brodolini found that €2.72bn had been allocated to social innovation as a secondary theme up to the end of 2016.

³ Istituto per la Ricerca Sociale (IRS) (2018). The European Social Fund: Beneficiaries' Experience in the Current Funding Period, Brussels: European Parliament's Committee on Employment and Social Affairs p. 12.

⁴ Discussion point mentioned during SIC's policy roundtable, Optimising the ESF+ for Social Innovation, October 12th 2018.

⁵ Available online: http://www.socialplatform.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/170601_SocialPlatform_ESF.pdf

- ESF stakeholders, including managing authorities and beneficiaries (those applying for funding), do not always have the skills and experience to design or operationalise new, innovative approaches to tackle social challenges. Some of our consultees highlighted the need to go much further than toolkits and guidance in addressing this.
- Complex regulations, processes and high administrative costs make it difficult to support social innovation through the ESF. One reason for this is that they make it unattractive for authorities to support smaller sized projects because the costs of administration are so high in relation to the grant size.⁶
- The ESF was not originally designed to support risky, experimental, locally-responsive projects, but increasingly it is being expected to do so. It is argued that the strong emphasis on results discourages projects from reaching out to riskier target users and discourages managing authorities from taking chances on early-stage projects where results are hard to predict. As a result, our consultees argued that the fund disproportionately favours the same 'usual suspects' both in terms of beneficiary organisations receiving funding, and end users participating in projects.

ESF+ addresses some of these problems, but could go further

In May 2018, the EC adopted a proposal for the multiannual financial framework 2021-27 on the future of the ESF.⁷ The new 'European Social Fund Plus' (ESF+) will combine several existing funds including ESF, the Youth Employment Initiative, the Employment and Social Innovation programme (EaSI) and others. Compared with the existing regulation, the new ESF+ proposal makes some important changes with regards to social innovation. These include:

- 01 More concrete indications of what ESF-supported social innovation looks like.** The new proposed regulation for ESF+ now offers a definition for social innovation - something the ESF regulation for the 2014-2020 stopped short of doing. With the incorporation of the EU Programme for Employment and Social Innovation (EaSI), a definition for 'social experimentation' is also offered.
- 02 A dedicated priority axis for social innovation.** The draft ESF+ proposal suggests that Member States will be required to select social innovation as a priority axis - dedicating at

[Accessed: 18/12/18]

⁶ For instance, Nantes Metropole assessed that the ratio between the cost of project development and the grant amount makes small projects (≤20-30K€) unfeasible. Cited at: EURO CITIES (2018) Lessons learned from cities' experiences with the ESF in 2014-2017, Brussels. p. 16 Available online: http://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EURO CITIES_report_on_ESF_and_cities_FINAL.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁷ See more: <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-new-boost-for-jobs-growth-and-investment/file-mff-esf> [Accessed 18/12/18]

least one priority to the implementation of a) social innovation and social experimentations, b) the upscaling of innovative approaches tested on a small scale (social experimentations) developed under the Employment and Social Innovation strand and other Union programmes - or both. This marks a significant reinforcing of social innovation as a priority of the ESF.

03 A higher co-financing rate to incentivise Member States to direct more of their national ESF+ allocation to innovative actions. Member States can allocate up to 5% of their national ESF+ allocation under shared management to Innovative Action priorities (Article 13) to take advantage of a more attractive co-financing rate, which has been increased to the maximum of 95%. While this will not increase the overall amounts for ESF, in some contexts this would see the current co-financing rate greatly increased, in particular for countries in the 'more developed region' category, like Belgium or Ireland, which can currently avail of a maximum co-financing rate of 50%. In theory if each Member State dedicated 5% of the Operational Programme to social innovation, this would earmark €5bn for social innovation priorities.

04 More centralised support for transnational social innovation initiatives (through indirect management). Some €200m has been earmarked for transnational cooperation to support transfer of innovative solutions and learning across countries through the Employment and Social Innovation (EaSI) strand. Unlike the current programming period, the EC proposes that this funding will be administered via indirect management (managed centrally by the EC, but with implementation being delegated to a managing authority for the entire programming period) rather than through 'shared management' with Member States. This is intended to reduce the administrative burden for national and subnational managing bodies.

Recommendations

The data and evidence on ESF in the 2014-20 programming period suggests ESF+ proposals could go further to ensure that funding for social innovation creates tangible and sustainable, resilient and scalable socially innovative outcomes that are relevant to final beneficiaries. We recommend that:

- 01** To incentivise Member States to prioritise social innovation, Article 13 of the ESF+ regulation should **require Member States to allocate a minimum of 5%** of their national ESF budget to support innovative actions.
- 02** To more effectively implement social innovation under ESF+, **the European Commission, Member States and key ESF implementing bodies should invite wider stakeholder involvement (communities, end users, social innovation practitioners, civil society organisations, social partners and local/regional actors) in defining and co-delivery of ESF+ priorities.** This can be achieved by:
 - Raising awareness, learning and exchange about the European Code of Conduct on Partnership to ensure that inclusive, meaningful partnerships are at the heart of defining ESF+ priorities through Partnership Agreements, Operational Programmes and Monitoring Committees.

- Ensuring training and technical assistance can be used to support more inclusive partnerships. Member States should ensure that partnership training is made available to public administration agencies, NGOs and other stakeholders who wish to increase their knowledge on implementation of the partnership principle in ESF+ (and ESIF) programmes and projects. Furthermore, we would advocate for a new and revised European Code of Conduct for Partnership to cover the post-2020 programming period.
- Broadening the focus of the ESF+ regulation to explicitly recognise cities, regional and local authorities and actors as strategic partners (where they are not already managing authorities) and call for their meaningful involvement in governance and all phases of the programming.

03 To strengthen the Employment and Social Innovation (EaSI) strand's ability to experiment with and transfer social innovation, the EC should **build a network of national competence centres to improve the support environment for ESF-supported social innovation**. These centres could:

- Develop training and capacity-building support for public leaders and officials (in partnership with training and education providers and schools of government).
- Offer managing bodies management support and a platform for learning and practice exchange.
- Provide capacity building for project promoters and stakeholders (especially smaller social and civil society actors).
- Develop practical guidance, support and technical assistance built on research, learning and practice for the design, preparation, implementation, evaluation, adaptation or replication of innovative actions.

04 To help mainstream and monitor the performance of cross-cutting social innovation policy approaches, the EC should **create a new European Observatory of Social Innovation Policy**.⁸ By complementing the actions of the Employment and Social Innovation strand, the Observatory would help deepen the relevance and impact of social experimentation by:

⁸ The concept for a European Observatory of Social Innovation Policy was outlined in SIC's Lisbon Declaration, which received high-level support from Carlos Moedas, Commissioner for Research, Science and Innovation, at Web Summit 2018 in Lisbon. Read more at: Social Innovation Community (2018) The Lisbon Declaration - Social Innovation As A Path to A Sustainable, Resilient and Inclusive Europe. Available online: https://www.siceurope.eu/sites/default/files/field/attachment/the_lisbon_social_innovation_declaration15.10_0.pdf [Accessed: 18/12/18]

- Boosting the impact of social experimentation through hands-on and demand-led support for relevant stakeholders⁹ in the design and comparative evaluation of social innovations.
- Identifying and validating high-potential social innovations, good practices and scalable solutions, which can be incorporated into national policy reform packages or replicated and scaled transnationally, through transnational learning networks.
- Designing transnational learning exercises between relevant managing bodies and projects to help adapt, replicate or scale promising social innovation pilots, experiments and programmes from elsewhere.

05 **The EC and Member States should launch interventions that encourage managing bodies and others to experiment with rules and regulation, and ensure they are proportionate and flexible to support social innovation.** Some examples of the ways the regulation could be experimented with include:

- Setting up (and agreeing with the EC) realistic 'light' targets in the Operational Programmes for social innovation-specific priorities.
- Establishing ESF+ Social Innovation Sandboxes to support administrative experimentation. These would be new mechanisms set up to create a controlled environment where standard rules and regulations can be relaxed so that managing bodies can prototype and test new regulatory arrangements (e.g. monitoring and eligibility requirements) that aim at addressing common social innovation barriers before implementation.
- Creating improved monitoring for Operational Programmes, so that indicators, milestones and targets are defined according to the stages or aims of social innovation or social experimentation projects.

⁹ As with the PROGRESS axis of EaSI currently, support should be made open to all public and/or private bodies, actors and institutions (including international organisations) who have an interest in using the ESF to support social experimentation (linked to the achievement of its policy objectives).

1. INTRODUCTION

Since 2008, Europe's renewed Social Agenda has explored how the European social model can be made more modern, inclusive, innovative and sustainable.¹⁰ Of the EU's many funding instruments, the European Social Fund is one of the most powerful tools for creating a more 'social Europe'. Moreover, since at least the early 2000s, it has supported social innovation. This has been broadly defined by the European Commission as the development of "new ideas, services and models to better address social issues", and invites input from public, private and civil society as a way to improve social services.¹¹ As we show in this report, the ESF has been a significant funder of social innovation during the 2014-2020 programming period.

EU policymakers are currently negotiating the EU's next long-term budget, the Multiannual Financial Framework for 2021-2027. In May 2018, the European Commission adopted proposals for a new Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) for 2021-2027. The new 'European Social Fund Plus' (ESF+) will combine several existing funds including ESF, the Youth Employment Initiative, the Employment and Social Innovation programme (EaSI) and others. The Commission proposed that over this period, ESF+ will have a budget of €101.2 billion.

The current ESF regulation explicitly encourages social innovation, as does the proposal for ESF+. However, many ESF stakeholders and beneficiaries report several challenges in attempting to use the fund for social innovation. These include a lack of capacity to effectively design, implement, evaluate and scale innovative actions, and a widespread misunderstanding of what social innovation is, and the rationale for supporting it.

The aim of this report is therefore to explore how the proposed ESF+ can be further enhanced to support more and better social innovation activities as a way to achieve its high level goals. It brings together analysis of ESF expenditure on social innovation, previous reports on ESF and social innovation and responses to the ESF+ proposals, with primary data from stakeholder interviews and roundtable discussions. It makes clear recommendations about further amendments to the ESF+ proposal, and for its eventual implementation in the 2021-2027 programming period.

¹⁰ European Commission (2010). What social Europe can do for you. Available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=4983&langId=en> [Accessed: 18/12/18]

¹¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1022>

Methodology

Document analysis

We conducted a review of the literature that aimed to: draw together existing analysis on how ESF 2014-2020 has been used for social innovation; explore the experiences of beneficiaries (recipients of ESF funding) and managing authorities in using ESF to support social innovation, and identify barriers and enablers in using ESF for social innovation; and draw together responses to the ESF+ proposal relevant to social innovation (including policy briefings and opinions from civil society organisations and other relevant stakeholders).

Expert interviews and online roundtables

We interviewed eight key stakeholders, including EU officials, representatives of civil society organisations (e.g. network organisations), ESF experts and others with a broad insight into ESF and social innovation. Interviews were semi-structured and carried out online and face-to-face.

In addition we engaged an additional eight stakeholders as part of two online roundtable discussions, in March and October 2018, and some follow-up discussions. The first roundtable discussed '*How can ESF support a more ambitious social innovation agenda?*' and was attended by five representatives from ESF managing authorities, EU member country governments and civil society organisations as well as six members of the SIC consortium. The second, framed more specifically on, '*How ESF+ can be optimised for social innovation?*', was attended by a representative of the Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion, and representatives from two European civil society networks: the European Anti-Poverty Network and the European Lifelong Learning Platform. Two members from the SIC consortium facilitated the discussion.

Analysis of ESF financial data

European Structural Fund and Investments (ESIF) data records financial information regarding five funds under the ESIF (ERDF, CF, ESF, EAFRD and EMFF).¹² In this report, the dataset 'ESIF 2014-2020 categorisation planned vs implemented details' was primarily used to explore ESF EU financial allocations to social innovation.¹³ This dataset records financial allocation across eight categorisation dimensions: intervention field, form of finance, territorial dimension, territorial delivery mechanism, thematic objective, ESF secondary theme, economic dimension, and location dimension. The

¹² Available online: <https://cohesiondata.ec.europa.eu/> [Accessed: 18/12/18]

¹³ Available online: <https://cohesiondata.ec.europa.eu/EU-Level/ESIF-2014-2020-categorisation-ERDF-ESF-CF-planned-/3kx-ekfq> [Accessed: 18/12/18]

dimension “ESF secondary theme” includes “social innovation” as one of several secondary themes, while the dimension “intervention field” includes “Community-Led Local Development”. Both of these fields were used for our analysis.

However, it is necessary to clarify at this point that these two dimensions do not fully capture the actual ESF financial allocation to social innovation. Not all countries have completed the “ESF secondary theme” categorisation: only around 66% of total planned ESF EU funding, €55.3 billion from 23 countries, has been classified into an “ESF secondary theme”. Further, the design of the dataset does not allow us to carry out cross-analysis between these two dimensions, so we cannot take figures from Community-Led Local Development under the dimension “intervention field” to complement analysis of social innovation under “ESF secondary theme”.

Our analyses were threefold. First, we explored the proportion of total ESF EU funding that has been planned to support social innovation under the “ESF secondary theme”. Then, we looked at the ‘implementation gap’, by comparing overall progress in deciding how to spend ESF EU funding with progress in deciding funding for social innovation. Lastly, we analysed ESF spend on Community-Led Local Development (CLLD) under “intervention field”.

FIGURE 1: DIAGRAMMATIC REPRESENTATION OF RESEARCH DESIGN

Structure of the report

This report is structured as follows:

- **Section 2** briefly reviews the policy context, looking at the emergence of, and rationale for, social innovation as a priority within the European Social Fund.
- **Section 3** explores progress in implementing ESF-supported social innovation by analysing data on ESF financial allocations and spend.
- **Section 4** pulls together qualitative data from document analysis, interviews and roundtables.
- **Section 5** explores the ESF+ proposals in more depth, highlighting changes from the current ESF regulation from the perspective of support for social innovation and synthesising relevant stakeholders' responses to the proposals.
- **Section 6** presents conclusions and recommendations on how ESF+ could be optimised for social innovation, both in its design and implementation.

2. THE EUROPEAN SOCIAL FUND AND SOCIAL INNOVATION

Set up in 1957, the European Social Fund (ESF) is the oldest of the EU's Structural Funds pursuing cohesion policy. It was set up under the Treaty of Rome with a view to improving workers' mobility and employment opportunities in the common market, and is the European Union's main financial instrument for investing in people. It works primarily by subsidizing occupational trainee and social inclusion projects, and to a lesser extent by supporting local development projects. The ESF framework is formulated by EU institutions and implemented by ESF managing bodies, often regional authorities, which launch calls for projects which require innovative actions and a results-oriented strategy.¹⁴

In the years since its establishment, the ESF's regulations and objectives have evolved in line with changes facing different Member States, as well as EU-level concerns. Important principles introduced over time include *subsidiarity* (which ensures that powers are exercised as close to the citizen as possible),¹⁵ *additionality* (which stipulates that financial allocations from the Structural and Investment Funds cannot result in a reduction of national structural expenditure in those regions);¹⁶ the *partnership principle*¹⁷ (which is significant today in the context of ESF-funded social innovation, as partnerships facilitate learning processes, can identify and implement innovative approaches, thus resulting in improved programming and implementation of funds, policy reforms and the mobilisation of additional and different kinds of resources).¹⁸ The kinds of initiatives funded through the ESF have also changed over time to take into account growing recognition of what works to facilitate inclusive and sustainable social cohesion for Europe. Indeed, as the influential 2010 BEPA report on social innovation noted:

"The lessons learned from both the Lisbon Strategy for Growth and Jobs and the financial crisis have revealed structural weaknesses and presented the social dimension of Europe in a new light: the well-held belief that economic growth creates employment and wealth to alleviate poverty has been disproved by recent events, and the time has now come to try new ways of bringing people out of

¹⁴ Sbaraglia, F. (2016). Who makes European Cohesion Policy: a practitioner's learning perspective. *Regional studies, regional science*, 3(1), 420-427.

¹⁵ <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/7/the-principle-of-subsidiarity> [Accessed: 18/12/18]

¹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/what/glossary/a/additionality/ [Accessed: 18/12/18]

¹⁷ "In the legislative framework for the 2014-2020 ESI Funds the partnership principle has been strengthened. Article 5 of the Common Provision Regulation (CPR) makes it compulsory for each ESI Fund programme to organise a partnership at all programming stages and at all levels. [...] Overall, the partnership principle adds value to the implementation of European public policies." Available online:

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/publications/studies/2016/implementation-of-the-partnership-principle-and-multi-level-governance-during-the-2014-2020-esi-funds [Accessed: 18/12/18]

¹⁸ EUROCITIES (2018) A smart investment in people: EUROCITIES position on ESF+. Available online: http://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EUROCITIES_statement_ESF_final.pdf [Accessed: 18/12/18]

poverty and promoting growth and well-being not only for, but also with, citizens.”¹⁹

Social innovation as an emerging priority of the ESF

It is in this broader context of changing societal demands and challenges, and growing recognition that past top-down approaches were not adequately addressing them, that social innovation has emerged as a priority within the ESF.

An early example of an ESF sub-programme that explicitly sought to support social innovation was the Community Initiative, EQUAL. It has been described as “the largest programme to support social innovation in the fields of social inclusion and employment ever.”²⁰ EQUAL ran between 2000 and 2006 and was used as a basis for the setting up transnational learning networks in the subsequent programming periods. The ex-post evaluation of EQUAL suggests it had a lasting impact on how the ESF is used to drive social innovation, particularly in that it highlighted a gap in the provision of services for certain target groups (such as migrants, ex-prisoners and ethnic minorities, such as Roma).²¹ It also underscored the need for more integrated approaches to economic, social and employment policy by demonstrating the limitations of fighting social exclusion and poverty through employment and jobs alone, and that growth and jobs were necessary, but not sufficient, to combat complex yet connected issues such as income disparities, regional disparities, gender and ethnic disparities or household hardships.²²

For 2014-2020, the total European Social Fund was set at €84bn. Rather than a ring-fenced fund for social innovation, the ESF Regulation 2013 stated that “the ESF shall promote social innovation within all areas falling under its scope”. It further specified that “support for social innovation contributes to making policies more responsive to social change. The ESF should encourage and support social enterprises and entrepreneurs as well as innovative projects taken on by non-governmental organisations and other actors within the social economy. In particular, testing and evaluating innovative solutions before scaling them up is instrumental in improving the efficiency of policies and thus justifies specific support from the ESF.” Article 9 of the 2013 ESF Regulation confirmed that social

¹⁹ BEPA (2010). Empowering People, Driving Change. Social Innovation in the European Union. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

²⁰ European Commission (2008). EQUAL opportunities for all: Delivering the Lisbon Strategy through social innovation and transnational cooperation. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities. p.6

²¹ Metis GmbH (2010). Ex post evaluation of the EQUAL Community Initiative (2000-2006). Vienna.

²² European Commission (2013). Guide to Social Innovation. Brussels: Regional and Urban Policy Publications, Office of the European Union, p. 7.

innovation is a cross-cutting principle of ESF, and should be promoted across all thematic objectives.²³ An incentive was provided to Member States in the form of a higher maximum co-financing rate for priority axes dedicated to social innovation. There was also a requirement on Member States to “set out the contribution of planned ESF-supported actions to [...] social innovation and transnational cooperation [...] where they are not covered by a dedicated priority axis”.

In the current programming period (2014-2020), there has also been an emergence of several finance measures aimed at increasing the capacity of social partners and NGOs. This capacity building of social partners and NGOs takes place for two main reasons. First, it is intended to strengthen such actors’ ability to deliver the policy objectives of the ESF in areas such as employment, education and social inclusion. Second, it is intended to strengthen wider participation of stakeholders in policy making and delivery: “Emphasis should be placed on strengthening their position for co-design, co-decision, co-production and co-evaluation vis-à-vis government and public administration. With a view to efficiency and effectiveness, and public sector innovation, the aim is to increase stakeholders’ efforts in partnership with the government and administration to deliver services to citizens and business.”²⁴

Additionally, in the 2014-2020 programming period, Community-Led Local Development (CLLD) can in theory be supported through any of the European Structural and Investment Funds (although its use is only mandatory in the EAFRD, under the LEADER measure). The use of integrated and bottom-up approaches like CLLD and other less formalised local initiatives within ESF signals an attempt to build community capacity, increase participation and ownership, and stimulate innovation (including social innovation), entrepreneurship and capacity for change by encouraging the development and discovery of untapped potential from within communities and territories.²⁵

²³ The full article reads as follows: Regulation (EU) No 1304/2013, 17 Dec 2013 **Article 9 – Social innovation:** 1. *The ESF shall promote social innovation within all areas falling under its scope, as defined in Article 3 of this Regulation, in particular with the aim of **testing, evaluating and scaling up** innovative solutions, including at the local or regional level, in order to address social needs in partnership with the relevant partners and, in particular, social partners. 2. Member States shall identify, either in their operational programmes or at a later stage during implementation, fields for social innovation that correspond to the Member States’ specific needs. The Commission shall facilitate **capacity building** for social innovation, in particular through supporting **mutual learning, establishing networks**, and disseminating and promoting good practices and methodologies.*

²⁴ Promoting Good Governance - European Social Fund Thematic Paper. p. 7. Available online: <http://ec.europa.eu/esf/BlobServlet?docId=444&langId=en> [Accessed: 03/12/18]

²⁵ European Commission (2014) Fact Sheet: Community-led Local Development. Available online: http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docgener/informat/2014/community_en.pdf [Accessed: 18/12/18]

The rationale for social innovation within ESF

Why does ESF support social innovation? Stakeholders consulted for this report noted that social innovation is not an end in itself but a means to an end. However, the reasons for promoting social innovation in ESF are perhaps more implicit than explicit. Based on document analysis and stakeholder interviews, we suggest there are five main reasons:

To identify emerging and unmet needs

The additionality principle requires ESF funding be invested in areas where the EU can offer "European added value" over public spending at national level. A justification for the funding is therefore that it must be directed towards initiatives that would not ordinarily be funded by national or regional authorities.

Rather than using the fund to maintain current public services, therefore, the ESF is intended to be more future-oriented, and to ensure that emerging and future challenges and needs are detected on the policy radar. All this explains the ESF's focus on tackling future challenges like the technological, economic and social changes transforming the world of work across Europe. Meanwhile, it is also recognised that public institutions and systems need to be more responsive to changing societal demands as they emerge. The migrant crisis, for example, intensified in the middle of the EU's current programming period.

To experiment with next-generation policies, services and solutions

The ESF is potentially a powerful tool to enable public authorities to test and evaluate new approaches, take risks and involve citizens and communities in shaping public employment and skills services so that they are more fit for purpose. The Social Investment Package (2013) positioned social innovation as a way to achieve these transformative objectives, "as an integral part of necessary adjustments by testing new policy approaches and selecting the most effective ones."²⁶

To help streamline and scale up innovations happening at Member State and subnational levels, it was envisaged that support from complementary social policy experimentation instruments like EaSI's PROGRESS axis would work by gathering evidence on their feasibility so that they can be scaled on a larger scale. Furthermore, these new demands for public organisations to setup and test experimental actions (including experiments to find new administrative solutions to better manage innovation and

²⁶ European Commission (2013) Communication From The Commission To The European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions. Towards Social Investment for Growth and Cohesion – including implementing the European Social Fund. Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52013DC0083&from=GA> [Accessed 18/12/18]

social experimentation) requires that they upskill, build up their ‘administrative and institutional capacity²⁷ and ‘modernise their public administrations’’^{28,29} (all of which are established concepts within the ESF).

To facilitate policy learning, upscaling and transfer

The concern with testing and scaling implies that the goal of ESF is to create an environment where high-potential innovative solutions are more easily detected and validated so that the most promising solutions would be adapted and scaled to new contexts across the EU-28. This objective is supported in theory by the establishment of learning platforms, such as the ESF Transnational Learning Network, and by mutual learning exercises like the Joint Action Plans (ESF JAP), which aim to exchange and disseminate learning about good practices through networks.

To strengthen society’s capacity to act

The ESF’s focus on ‘good governance’ can also be seen in the broader context of seeking to create more relational, responsive state arrangements that enhance the relationship and partnerships between government, citizens and other stakeholders. The aim here is for public institutions to become “flexible enough to react to the many societal challenges, open for dialogue with the public, and able to introduce new policies and deliver better services.”³⁰

To deliver the European Pillar of Social Rights

Looking ahead, it is therefore evident why the ESF+ is seen as the main tool to deliver on the policy objective of “A more social Europe - Implementing the European Pillar of Social Rights.” The importance of the partnership and subsidiarity principles - which are core to both the ESF and social innovation - are recognised as having a key role in supporting the objectives of the Pillar: “Most of the tools to deliver on the Pillar are in the hands of local, regional and national authorities, as well as social partners, and civil society at large”.³¹

²⁷ European Commission (2014). Programming Period 2014-2020, Monitoring and Evaluation of European Cohesion Policy: European Social Fund - Guidance Document on Indicators of Public Administration Capacity Building. Available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=14144&langId=en> [Accessed 18/12/18]

²⁸ Read more at: <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=325&langId=en> [Accessed 18/12/18]

²⁹ European Commission (2017) Quality of Public Administration: A Toolbox for Practitioners. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

³⁰ European Commission (2014) Promoting Good Governance - European Social Fund Thematic Paper. p. 6. Available online: <http://ec.europa.eu/esf/BlobServlet?docId=444&langId=en> [Accessed: 18/12/18]

³¹ See more at: http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-17-1004_en.pdf [Accessed: 18/12/18]

In practice: how can social innovation help deliver ESF's goals?

Case studies of ESF-funded social innovation help to illustrate some of the specific ways in which social innovation approaches can help deliver ESF objectives.

Focusing on users' needs, rather than institutional needs

Regardless of whether an innovation is initiated through top-down or bottom-up mechanisms, social innovation can shift the logic from delivering solutions *to users*, to developing and implementing solutions *with users*. This shift requires a change in dominant modes of working within the public sector towards more collaborative, participative ways of working.

'Improving Equality and Empowerment through Person-Centred Energy Advice Service' (EPCAS), Scotland³²

The EPCAS project is a 12-month proof-to-concept initiative devised by Mydex CIC, the University of the West of Scotland, Linstone Housing Association, Renfrewshire Council and Recovery Across Mental Health (RAMH). Using digital innovation, the objective of the project is to tackle fuel poverty through co-designing data journeys with individuals who are accessing Energy Advocacy services so that they are more aligned with the user rather than organisational needs. The project was awarded £139,566 of ESF funding.

Partners in the project mapped typical journeys when accessing certain services and identified with users the key barriers and 'pain points' that were leading to difficult experiences. These included, for example, the need to continuously reapply for discounts and grants, repeatedly giving out details and stating their financial circumstances, which are particularly challenging for individuals experiencing mental health issues. Partners visited the homes of people accessing these services to understand contextually how this interaction with energy advocacy services currently operates and where these 'pain points' were emerging.

From these insights one of the partners, Mydex CIC, developed open-source software to produce a test base of newly designed web applications to bring the process online and adapt service access to user needs. These were then built into a Web Application Generator (WAG) where users were able to test and redesign these apps to enable better ways of storing and accessing their data, and to actively shape their

³² See more at: <https://medium.com/epcas>

interactions with energy advice services.

The project is coming to the end of its 12-month timeframe and is a few months into the launch of the WAG. The aim is that this platform and iterative co-design process will be used to improve other services. By focusing on the interface in which users and services interact, EPACS envisions a more bottom-up approach to services in which users are empowered and more in control of their lives.

Unlocking and sustaining new forms of social and human capital

Social innovation can create new social relationships or collaborations between public, private, and third sector organisations, and end users, thereby empowering civil society actors and others to act. In the context of the ESF, this can mean shifting from narrower labour activation initiatives to more holistic, person-centred approaches, which take into account the broader emotional and social needs of individuals or groups, and in particular those that intend to improve the social and human capital of marginalised and underserved individuals or groups.

Vives Emplea, Spain³³

In a climate of increasing economic uncertainty, individuals experiencing social exclusion have felt the most impact in Spanish communities. The focus of the Vives Emplea project, which received €5,837,473 in ESF funding, was to address and mitigate social exclusion within the arenas of employment and education through an innovative teamwork methodology.

Where public services are being cut and the civic system is increasingly disconnected from those that need it most, Vives Emplea uses an innovative approach which recognises the agency of individuals and the power of the collective to transform lives and facilitate participation in employment and citizenship.

The project uses teamwork between individuals experiencing entrenched disadvantage and social exclusion to work together and generate a support platform on which to develop skills and self-efficacy. The process involves a number of sessions including team-building, individual coaching and contact with companies to recognise their own strengths and aspirations and build them into a sense of employability.

It has been successful on several levels which all impact on each other. It has, on a personal level, supported individuals to develop confidence and motivation to improve their own lives and ambitions; but it has also contributed to changing perceptions of unemployed people and how society should not see them as lacking but as individuals with strengths that must be supported and encouraged. This success is reflected in the numbers with 54% of participants now in employment and 29% partaking in education.

ESF funding has enabled the project to scale up to other parts of the country by building evaluative mechanisms into its process so that it can be replicable across other regions within Spain but flexible enough to adapt to the varying needs of those different communities.

³³ See more at: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/projects/spain/working-together-to-increase-employability

Looking beyond the public sector alone for solutions

Social innovation is often described as a 'boundary-blurring' activity that assumes new ideas emerge when stakeholders from different sectors are brought closer together around shared goals.³⁴

Partnership is both an important feature of ESF-supported social innovation³⁵ and a central principle of the ESF. Better partnerships between public, private and third sector organisations have the potential to unleash social innovations that are more closely aligned with target users' real needs.

Brno, Czech Republic – using the ESF to radically redesign homelessness provision³⁶

The Housing First approach has been proven to end long-term homelessness among people with high support needs. First devised in Finland, the model differs from typical homelessness services. Instead of requiring a homeless person first to qualify for housing (e.g. by demonstrating they are engaging with addiction services), it views housing as a right, and provides the person with a house first, as well as a range of wider support services. Using a €369,656 ESF grant, the Municipality of Brno in partnership with IQ Roma Servis, a pro-Roma social service provider, and the University of Ostrava adapted the Housing First approach to end family homelessness.

This is the first time a randomised controlled trial has been used in the Czech Republic to gather evidence on the impact of a social project. 50 randomly assigned homeless families are provided housing and intensive case management. Outcomes will be compared with those of a control group of 100 families. The project has demonstrated positive impacts on family well-being, children's behaviour, security and employment. The partnership approach has facilitated a more integrated city system to tackling homelessness to ensure all needs are met. If the results of this implementation turn out to be positive, other municipalities and national actors will adopt the approach.

³⁴ Nicholls, A., Murdock, A. (eds.) (2012). *Social Innovation: Blurring Boundaries to Reconfigure Markets*.

³⁵ A key finding from SIC's 2017 State of the Union policy report was that all the examples of employment-related social innovation case studies exhibited cross-sector collaboration between partners including local and national governments, funding bodies, civil society organisations and in certain cases, research institutions or end-users. See more at: N. Ahmed et al. (2017) D5.6: Annual State of the Union Report – Part 2: How is EU employment policy driving social innovation? p. 64.

https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/how_is_eu_employment_policy_driving_social_innovation.pdf [Accessed: 18/12/18]

³⁶ https://www.feantsa.org/download/fea-007-17-eu-funding_ok7885765817773537732.pdf

Building on bottom-up and participatory approaches (such as Community-Led Local Development and other local initiatives)

Bottom-up and participatory approaches recognise the need for new modes of policy-making and governance arrangements that take into account local or marginalised voices. In turn, this can help tackle the public political disaffection and perceptions of there being a democratic deficit which beleaguer many of our governments today. Furthermore, bottom-up and integrated approaches like CLLD and other local initiatives create many of the necessary pre-conditions for social innovation, and in the framework of the ESF, establish an underexploited way to approach social cohesion, “tackling well-known problems, but also determining procedures that lead to the identification of unexpressed needs and innovative development strategies.”³⁷

Improving social cohesion in Kujawsko-Pomorskie, Poland³⁸

Kujawsko-Pomorskie has the second highest level of unemployment in Poland and a population living in extreme poverty that is above the national average. The region's managing authority has developed an approach to enable various parts of the region to access €36.5M of CLLD funding in order to develop local infrastructure and facilitate integration and pathways into employment. For example, a partnership has developed in Krajna and Paluki using combined funds from the ESF, ERDF and the EAFRD to utilise a CLLD approach to tackle a variety of challenges such as an ageing population, low levels of professional qualifications, and a poor labour and social infrastructure.

The funding from ESF, €700,000, specifically focuses on facilitating an active community and the development of visible and accessible public spaces and groups such as youth centres, community hubs and job clubs. This aims to engender a person-centred approach to tackling social exclusion in which families and individuals can participate in a supportive locality that provides opportunities for building social capital and individual and collective agency.

In five years' time, the initiative expects to have assisted in the creation of new businesses and consequently of new jobs in the local area. In total it aims to have supported 555 individuals at risk of social exclusion with a portion of those to have employment by 2023.

³⁷ Antonio Servillo, L. (2017) CLLD under ERDF/ESF in the EU: A stock-taking of its implementation. European Commission, DG REGIO and DG Employment, p. 42.

³⁸ See more at: https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/fpfis/cms/farnet2/sites/farnet/files/publication/farnet-g10_starting-clld-implementation-in-practice_en.pdf See also: https://ec.europa.eu/esf/transnationality/filedepot_download/594/4

3. HOW EFFECTIVELY IS ESF BEING USED FOR SOCIAL INNOVATION, IN PRACTICE?

How much ESF EU funding has been allocated to social innovation?

As noted earlier, countries may choose to make social innovation a 'priority axis' within their ESF Operational Programmes (OPs). In a 2018 report for DG-EMPL, Fondazione Giacomo Brodolini (FGB) found that just 11 OPs (of a total of 187) from six Member States had allocated funds for social innovation through Priority Axes.³⁹ These allocations totalled just under **€980m**, or 0.8% of total ESF EU allocations.⁴⁰

However, social innovation is a cross-cutting approach and can also be supported under other named priorities. Countries can therefore categorise projects as falling into the social innovation 'secondary theme' (one of seven cross-cutting ESF themes). Our analysis shows that, as of the end of 2017, **€2.84bn** ESF planned spend had been categorised under the social innovation secondary theme.⁴¹ This also reveals a much wider range of countries and OPs using ESF to support social innovation activities - some 90 OPs from 23 Member States have categorised spend under the social innovation secondary theme.

Even so, this may not accurately reflect total planned spend on social innovation. Although not all EU countries have allocated funding to social innovation as an ESF secondary theme (those that have not include Cyprus, Ireland, Latvia, Sweden and Slovenia), they might in practice fund socially innovative projects under other priority axes or themes. Not all countries or OPs had completed the ESF secondary theme categorisation at the time this analysis was undertaken. The general lack of awareness about the concept of social innovation can mean that innovative ESF-funded initiatives are not recognised as such, and so can go undetected. On the other hand, Member States may label activities social innovation, without fully understanding the concept or its goals.

In addition, while the guidelines for ESF secondary theme categorisation state that multiple secondary themes can be selected for each planned expenditure, it is possible that in some case countries have

³⁹ Fondazione G. Brodolini. (2018). ESF Performance and Thematic Reports the ESF Support to Social Innovation, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available online:

<http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=738&langId=en&pubId=8107&furtherPubs=yes> [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁴⁰ This figure does not include ESF national co-financing amounts.

⁴¹ This figure is based on our own analysis of ESF planned expenditure up to the end of 2017. Source: ESIF 2014-2020 categorisation ERDF-ESF-CF planned vs implemented. Available online:

<https://cohesiondata.ec.europa.eu/2014-2020/ESIF-2014-2020-categorisation-ERDF-ESF-CF-planned-/3kx-ekfq>

not selected all relevant themes. This may explain, for example, why not all OPs that include social innovation as one of their priority axes claim the same amount on social innovation under ESF secondary theme - and indeed why some countries appear to have no planned expenditure at all under the ESF secondary theme. In fact, the report by FGB cited earlier found that 84% of OPs claimed in their Annual Implementation Reports (AIRs) for 2016 that they had supported some social innovation activity.⁴²

Support for social innovation is uneven across countries

While most countries have earmarked some ESF for social innovation, the majority of activity appears to be concentrated in a relatively small number of places. Some 71% of ESF allocated to the social innovation secondary theme comes from just six countries: Germany, Portugal, Poland, Estonia, Austria and Italy.

Meanwhile, as Figure 2 shows, most countries only plan to spend small amounts of their total ESF EU budgets on social innovation. There are just five countries that have allocated over 10% of their budgets to social innovation activities.

⁴² Fondazione G. Brodolini. (2018) ESF Performance and Thematic Reports the ESF Support to Social Innovation, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available online: <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=738&langId=en&pubId=8107&furtherPubs=yes> [Accessed: 18/12/18]

FIGURE 2: ESF EU FUNDING FOR SOCIAL INNOVATION AS A PROPORTION OF EACH COUNTRY'S OVERALL ESF BUDGET

Proportion of ESF EU Budget on Social Innovation under ESF Secondary Theme

Note: this chart excludes Denmark, which has no 'planned' allocation for the social innovation secondary theme, although it does have 'decided' funding under this theme.

The implementation gap

Further analysis shows significant variation across Member States in the extent to which they have 'decided' their ESF funds for social innovation - that is, committed to spending it on specified operations.

This could indicate that member countries are finding it difficult to spend their ESF allocations on social innovation. However, it is also possible that they are behind with ESF spend more generally, and that social innovation is not a special case. To explore this, we looked at Member States' progress in 'deciding' ESF spend.

Figure 3 highlights the differences between Member States in terms of the proportion of their total planned ESF EU funds which had been decided by the end of 2017.⁴³ As shown in the figure, Ireland has decided all its ESF budget of €480 million. Seventeen out of 28 countries have decided on over 50% of their overall ESF funding allocation. However, some countries have made very little progress in decisions, with Romania, Croatia and Cyprus having decided on less than 30% of their overall ESF allocation.

FIGURE 3. PROPORTION OF OVERALL ESF EU FUNDING ALLOCATION 'PLANNED' AND 'DECIDED' BY END OF 2017, BY MEMBER STATE

Proportion of ESF EU funding allocation 'decided' by 2017

For funds allocated to the social innovation secondary theme, a similar picture emerges. In total, by the

⁴³ Planned amount refers to funding allocation at planning stage, and decided amount refers to the eligible costs that have decided to be allocated to specific operations and beneficiaries.

end of 2017, €1.64 billion had been decided out of €2.84 billion planned spend on social innovation - around 58%. However, at a country level, there is considerable variation. Some countries have decided a large proportion of their planned social innovation allocations - or even decided to spend more ESF on social innovation than originally planned. Among them, three countries account for 62% of total 'decided' social innovation spend: Spain (28%), Germany (22%) and Estonia (12%).

Some others, however, have made less progress. Figure 4 highlights the differences in planned and decided spending at the end of 2017. As at the overall level, Romania, Croatia, Lithuania, and Netherlands have seen very little or no progress in their spending decisions for social innovation.

FIGURE 4. PROPORTION OF ESF ALLOCATION TO SOCIAL INNOVATION SECONDARY THEME 'PLANNED' AND 'DECIDED' BY END OF 2017, BY MEMBER STATE

Planned and decided ESF EU funding for ESF secondary theme "Social Innovation" (2017)

Given the current programming period is well into its second half, we would expect more progress on spending decisions at this stage for some Member States. As Figure 5 shows, thirteen of the countries that have allocated ESF to social innovation as a secondary theme had 'decided' 30% or more of this funding by the end of 2017 - and might therefore be considered roughly 'on track' with their spend. Denmark, in addition, had decided to spend some of its ESF allocation under the social innovation secondary theme even though this was not originally planned. Meanwhile, nine countries had decided less than 30% of their social innovation secondary theme allocations, with some significantly behind.

It is clear, therefore, that some countries have had difficulties or delays in spending their ESF allocations for social innovation, but also that ESF spend generally has been delayed for some countries. To explore whether there is evidence that ESF spend on social innovation is particularly

challenging, we compared overall decided ESF spend against funding decided specifically for social innovation. For this analysis we excluded three outlier countries - Malta, Spain and the UK - which had decided to spend considerably more on social innovation than their original planned allocations, to avoid chart distortion.

In Figure 5, the top right segment categorises countries which have made reasonable or strong progress in their decided spend both overall and for social innovation. In contrast, the bottom left-hand segment shows two countries (Croatia and Romania) are lagging behind in terms of their progress on decided spend for ESF overall and for social innovation. The top-left hand segment shows seven countries that have made good progress in deciding their overall ESF spend but which have made notably less progress with deciding their social innovation spend.

FIGURE 5. DECIDED ESF FUNDING OVERALL VS. DECIDED FUNDING FOR SI, BY MEMBER STATE

ESF EU funding allocation progress Overall VS Social Innovation

It appears therefore that for around a third of countries, using ESF for social innovation is particularly

challenging. This may be a quirk of the data - it is possible that this reflects difficulties defining activities as social innovation and/or a failure to categorise activities appropriately under the ESF dimensions. However, as we describe in the next section, our qualitative research and literature review suggests that there are some specific challenges in using ESF to support social innovation.

ESF spend on Community-Led Local Development (CLLD)

The gap in spending progress is even starker when analysing progress in spending decisions for ESF funding for Community-Led Local Development (CLLD). The general consensus around CLLD is that it is a precondition for social innovation but is an under-exploited way to approach social cohesion, “tackling well-known problems, but also determining procedures that lead to the identification of unexpressed needs and innovative development strategies”.⁴⁴

As Figure 6 shows, across the majority of Member States that categorized CLLD activities under the dimension “intervention field”,⁴⁵ there is a significant lack of progress in ESF spending decision-making. Romania and Portugal had high allocations for CLLD spend at the beginning of the programming period but by the end of 2017 had only decided on 1% of that budget. Greece planned a more modest ESF expenditure on CLLD but has not yet recorded any decisions. All three of these countries appear to have dedicated only a small proportion of their social innovation and CLLD funds by the end of 2017.

Spain and France have also yet to decide on any CLLD spend, but were planning only modest spend in this area and both countries are ahead of projected spend (significantly so in the case of Spain) for social innovation, so issues of classification may explain these differences. On the other hand, Hungary has significantly surpassed its planned CLLD spend. This may represent an alternative classification of funds, which could explain the relatively low level of decisions for social innovation projects noted in Figure 4 above. However, it should be noted that since CLLD and social innovation are classified in different ways, under different dimensions of ESF, it is not possible to state with certainty that over-spend in CLLD is a misclassification of anticipated social innovation spend, or vice-versa.

⁴⁴ Antonio Servillo, L. (2017) CLLD under ERDF/ESF in the EU: A stock-taking of its implementation. European Commission, DG REGIO and DG Employment, p. 42.

⁴⁵ Data categorised under the dimension “Territorial Delivery Mechanism - Community-led Local Development”, despite some differences in decided levels, reflects a similar trend.

FIGURE 6. PLANNED AND DECIDED ESF SPENDING FOR INTERVENTION FIELD 'CLLD' ACROSS EU COUNTRIES

Planned and decided ESF EU funding for intervention field "Community-led Local Development Strategy"

4. CHALLENGES IN USING ESF TO SUPPORT SOCIAL INNOVATION

Our qualitative research and synthesis of other relevant literature highlights several practical reasons why ESF managing authorities appear to have problems using current ESF programmes to fund social innovation.

Key decision makers are still unaware of what social innovation means for them

According to some of the experts consulted for this study, the rationale for using the ESF to support social innovation is too implicit and not well articulated. The concept and goals of social innovation and social experimentation are not well understood by stakeholders, particularly in the context of delivering a more social Europe. This may be one of the unintended consequences of ‘mainstreaming’ social innovation in the current programming period.⁴⁶

As a result, Member States and regional authorities seem to lack awareness about what social innovation is and what the benefits of supporting it are. In turn, this contributes to a lack of coordination, buy-in and support for social innovation at key levels, and a failure to allocate funding to social innovation priorities. Compounding this further, many ESF managing authorities operate at a remove from other government agencies, and consequently there can be disconnect between their activities and policies and those led by other public agencies and leaders.

Some of our consultees noted that Member States can be fiercely resistant to using part of their national ESF allocations for social innovation, preferring to allocate funding to other policy priorities - “social innovation is not one of them most of the time.”⁴⁷ This can result in what one consultee referred to as “structural inertia” - with a lot of funding tied to top-down priorities and in some instances “the propping up of failing public employment service actors.”⁴⁸

The potential of multi-stakeholder partnerships is not being exploited

Past research by SIC has pointed to the importance of partnerships as a way to catalyse social innovation using the ESF: shared ownership and participation by social partners and civil society is key to effective delivery of social innovation, and in some cases has enabled social partners to scale their impact.⁴⁹ In practice, however, managing authorities are often not able, or not incentivised, to create

⁴⁶ European Commission official, SIC online roundtable, October 2018.

⁴⁷ European Commission official, SIC online roundtable, October 2018.

⁴⁸ Expert interview

⁴⁹ N. Ahmed et al. (2017) D5.6: Annual State of the Union Report – Part 2: How is EU employment policy driving social innovation?

effective partnerships, coordinate between different agencies, or lead actions that involve multiple stakeholders.

Part of this can be explained by the very process of partnering having its difficulties, often because partners underestimate the amount of time and resources they need to invest in order to collaborate effectively.⁵⁰ However, a number of examples illustrate the extent to which multi-stakeholder partnerships, and a failure to leverage them effectively, poses a challenge to the potential of the ESF to support social innovation. For example, a survey carried out by Social Platform found that most managing authorities had not involved civil society as a partner in the design and implementation of funding, even though they are obliged to do so.⁵¹ A review of the European Code of Conduct on Partnership (ECCP) carried out by the ESF Partnerships Transnational Network finds that managing authorities need to make more efforts to go beyond compliance at the institutional level when putting the principle into practice.⁵²

Our research suggests rules and processes may hinder broader partnerships with stakeholders, such as smaller third sector and civil society organisations, who can launch social innovation projects. Currently, many eligibility rules disadvantage such organisations as they are unable to cover the true costs of projects. For example, not being able to claim management costs, payroll, ICT, archive and interest charges means third sector organisations have to find the money to pay for these costs.⁵³ The value of involving more diverse actors, particularly smaller actors with direct link to target groups, in Partnership Agreements, Operational Programmes and Monitoring Committees and in accessing the funding therefore needs to be better recognised as a pre-condition for social innovation.

Difficulties in building the social innovation capacity and skills of key stakeholders

ESF stakeholders, including managing authorities and beneficiaries (those applying for funding), do not always have the skills and experience to design or operationalise new, innovative approaches to tackle social challenges. As one roundtable participant noted, “managers from national authorities are coordinators - but the problem is they are not social innovation content experts”.⁵⁴

⁵⁰ ESN Transnational news n.6, May 2018. Available online:

<https://ec.europa.eu/esf/transnationality/filedepot/folder/39> [Accessed 10.09.18]

⁵¹ http://www.socialplatform.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/170601_SocialPlatform_ESF.pdf

⁵² Thematic Network on Partnership (2018) Initial findings and recommendations from European Code of Conduct on Partnership (ECCP) Review. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/esf/transnationality/filedepot_download/564/1592

⁵³ See more at: http://www.parliament.scot/S4_EuropeanandExternalRelationsCommittee/Inquiries/SCVO.pdf
Accessed 13.12.18]

⁵⁴ Social innovation practitioner, SIC online roundtable: How can the ESF+ be optimised for social innovation?

Past research carried out by SIC supports this claim. It found that some managing authorities and other regional actors are seen to be resistant to innovation and new ways of working.⁵⁵ This was seen by experts we consulted as both a cultural and capacity issue. Managing authorities have fallen into ‘safe’ and familiar modes of working (for example with regards to technical reporting), rather than exploring how to operationalise new, innovative approaches to tackling policy challenges, or working differently themselves. This view was expressed by some of the ESF beneficiaries we consulted for this study. One in particular spoke about the challenges that came about when trying to develop a local socially innovative solution within a management framework that was not fit for purpose: “The funding approach was too rigid. There was no space to refine the project’s approach based on learning that emerged. What we needed was for funding to be managed using an agile or lean approach, when in reality it was being funded using a waterfall approach”.⁵⁶

Some consultees acknowledged there is also a lack of adequate support to help address the innovation capacity gap of many public organisations lacking the resources, skills or know-how to operationalise innovations. Furthermore, even where social innovation is being supported with relative success, there can be inadequate support to ensure pilot innovative actions will be sustained and institutionalised after the programme period. For instance, a failure to use public procurement to support innovative products or services means that a great deal of innovation activity is discontinued and ultimately wasted.⁵⁷

Project beneficiaries (especially smaller social or civil society actors) can also encounter challenges in accessing specialist services they need to effectively design, prepare, implement, evaluate, adapt or replicate innovative actions. Difficulties can arise for beneficiaries who have particular capacity building or training needs (such as developing a marketing plan or accessing management training), but find they are unable to use project funding to access specialist professional support because such expenses cannot be reimbursed.

October 12th, 2018.

⁵⁵ N. Ahmed et al. (2017). D5.6: Annual State of the Union Report – Part 2: How is EU employment policy driving social innovation?

⁵⁶ Interview with ESF project beneficiary

⁵⁷ For instance, the Innovation Funding Mechanism at the ESF Department Flanders’ has recognised there is a need to revisit how its funding and support prioritises activities that will facilitate organisational learning and institutionalisation. Possible adaptations to the IFM are underway to help better sustain and embed innovations, so that promoters are more encouraged and prepared to adopt innovations beyond the pilot stage. The ESF department is, for example, experimenting with approaches to help organisations that receive funding from its “mainstream” calls to increase their overall innovation capacity and culture (in effect to become “learning organisations”).

ESF processes, rules and regulations are not perceived to be well tailored to support social innovation projects

There is a strong perception among Member States and managing authorities that regulations, processes and high administrative costs make it difficult to support social innovation through the ESF. Consultees argued that the ESF is not well designed to support risky, experimental, locally-responsive social innovation projects.

One reason for this is that it can be unattractive for authorities to support smaller sized projects because the costs of administration are so high in relation to the grant size. For instance, Nantes Metropole (a sub-regional authority) found that the ratio between the cost of project development and the grant amount makes small projects ($\leq 20\text{-}30\text{K€}$) unfeasible.⁵⁸ This can work to discourage small, nimble locally-embedded innovative organisations from submitting projects.

This point was further reinforced by a recent report produced by the European Parliament exploring ESF beneficiaries' experiences in the current programming period. The report notes that "implementation of social innovation projects often clashes with rules and administrative systems that were designed for traditional vocational training actions."⁵⁹ While this implies that ESF rules may be a barrier for social innovation, consultees also suggested that such issues may relate to interpretations of the rules at national or regional levels. For instance, our consultation found that:

- The perceived over-emphasis on results discourages projects from reaching out to riskier end beneficiaries and discourages managing authorities from taking chances on early-stage projects where results are hard to predict.
- Delays in payments to beneficiaries can impact on implementation periods creating shorter delivery time frames to act on complex issues.

Some of this may be the result of 'gold-plating' (over complex rules resulting from fear of non-compliance) and resistance to working differently by Member States and managing authorities, rather than 'official' ESF rules and regulations. For instance, one European Commission official consulted for this study responded to the comment that about being too results driven that:

"The only theoretical risk would be if social innovation actions were included in the Performance Reserve and hence in the milestones and targets. This would only

⁵⁸ EUROCITIES (2018). Lessons learned from cities' experiences with the ESF in 2014-2017, Brussels. p. 16 Available online: http://nws.euocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EUROCITIES_report_on_ESF_and_cities_FINAL.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁵⁹ IRS - Istituto per la Ricerca Sociale (2018). The European Social Fund: Beneficiaries' Experience in the Current Funding Period, Brussels: European Parliament's Committee on Employment and Social Affairs. , p. 65

happen if an Operational Programme allocated a very significant part of its resources to social innovation, which does not happen. And even if it did, only output indicators would be assessed under the Performance Framework (that would be for example number of tests conducted, number of models tested, for example). There are no sanctions for unmet milestones and targets.”⁶⁰

Furthermore, the ESF’s payment mechanism (based on short-term outcomes and the reimbursement of eligible costs)⁶¹ can make it difficult to implement innovative financing options, such as social impact bonds (a results-based form of social impact investment, where private investors provide capital to launch or expand innovative social services that provide a public good) within ESF. This does not make this impossible, however, as some Member States have shown. The issue seems rather to be a lack of sustained administrative experiments looking at how the ESF can improve its support for these kind of approaches.

Whether arising at EU or national levels, delays in payments also pose a major challenge for beneficiaries (particularly smaller organisations). In practice, issues such of the high costs of administering the ESF can result in the fund disproportionately favouring the same ‘usual suspects’ both in terms of beneficiary organisations receiving funding, and end users participating in projects. However, it seems that many of the perceived barriers to using the ESF for social innovation could be addressed through education and training for managing authorities and others.

Support for social experimentation and transnational cooperation is too limited

Inadequate institutional support for social experimentation results in a failure to sustain innovative solutions beyond project periods, and means that not enough is done to ensure that there are a clear pathways for bottom-up innovations to eventually scale transnationally.

Dedicated EU-level instruments like the EaSI PROGRESS axis were introduced in the current programming period to sit alongside the ESF and meet a recognised need “to generate, test and spread innovative policy solutions to foster sustainable long-term growth and jobs, reduce divergence between the Member States, and make progress towards reducing social inequality.”⁶² However, it is evident that a clear gap exists between the ambition and reality of what the complementary social experimentation

⁶⁰ Expert consulted by Nesta

⁶¹Fondazione G. Brodolini. (2018). ESF Performance and Thematic Reports the ESF Support to Social Innovation, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available online: <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=738&langId=en&pubId=8107&furtherPubs=yes> [Accessed: 18/12/18]

⁶² Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion. (2013). EaSI, new EU umbrella programme for employment and social policy. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

instruments like PROGRESS axis could expect to achieve given its limited budget. While EaSI's total budget for the 2014-2020 period was €1 billion, a much smaller amount of financial support (a maximum of €100 million - or 0.1% of EaSI's budget) has been allocated to social policy experimentation. Our consultations suggest that programme stakeholders need ad hoc guidance that might be better delivered through embedded support rather than funded projects.⁶³

Furthermore, past research by SIC found that less formalised support initiatives like the ESF Transnational Cooperation Platform's learning networks are seen by practitioners as being of great value to support dissemination and exchanging of good practices. However, consultees argue that they need to be more intensive and have a broader mandate and more resources if they are to make a lasting sustainable impact or to help drive necessary adaptations to the administrations of participating countries. As one network facilitator of the Thematic Network on Public Administration and Governance mentioned: "the network is bringing cutting-edge thinking on public management as well as EU added value by exposing colleagues from across the EU to different paradigms and associated practices as well as very different contexts that make it clear they need to do their own thinking."

'Hacking' the ESF

In spite of the barriers to using the ESF for social innovation, some managing authorities and others are using experimentation and creativity to reconcile the goals of supporting innovative actions with current rules and regulation. Examples directly supporting social innovation include:

- **Experimenting with national tax policy to make use of innovative financing options:** Portugal Social Innovation, an ESF-funded initiative designed to grow social impact investment in Portugal, encountered a number of challenges when looking to use the ESF to launch social impact bonds in support of social innovation projects. The biggest of these arose from the difficulties in attracting private capital because EU funds prohibit remunerating investors. Portugal Social Innovation cannot pay more than expenses to investors, in effect making this a recycling of financing rather than an investment. To sidestep some of these challenges, Portugal Social Innovation has experimented with the national tax system, introducing a tax relief/fiscal incentive for investments in SIBs which has been recognized in the Internal Revenue Code (Corporate Income Tax) as an "expense" for the year, with an increase of 130% in the amount invested.⁶⁴
- **Experimenting with multi-funded approaches using the ESF and other ESIF funds:** The managing authority for CLLD in Sweden was faced with the difficulty of combining four EU

⁶³ See more at: <https://ec.europa.eu/esf/transnationality/content/public-administration-and-governance-unconventional-network-impressive-results> [Accessed: 18/12/18]

⁶⁴ See more at: <http://www.socialinnovationacademy.eu/portugal-social-innovation/> [Accessed 13.12.18]

programmes that have different regulations and which are managed by different authorities. To overcome a number of the setbacks that were delaying project implementation, a local fund coordination group was established in Gothenburg, gathering representatives from relevant municipal programmes and processes and linking political decisions on the municipal level to those on regional, national and EU levels.⁶⁵

- **Using the deliverables model as a way to help social innovation beneficiaries access professional support:** Rigid rules around the eligibility of certain costs has meant that in the past project beneficiaries have not been able to access specialist training or professional supports because the cost of training would not be reimbursed. Portugal Social Innovation has experimented with an approach of using agreed deliverables, where beneficiaries co-define a 'deliverable product' (such as PowerPoint presentation or a marketing plan) which will be the result of an interaction with the training specialist. Project beneficiaries present the product to meet the deliverable requirements. However, in practice the real expenses are incurred in securing the agreed specialist training, meaning that beneficiaries can now access sought-after training and capacity building support they could not have in the past.
- **Using the fund to reach smaller social actors:** Nantes Metropole advises small operators to work as subcontractors with large operators to overcome this entry barrier.⁶⁶
- **Centralising administration tasks so that small ESF projects can focus on implementation:** Karlstad City is running five ESF funded projects in 2014-2020 with a total budget of just over €20 million (199 million SEK) of which EU co-financing accounts for €12 million (119 million SEK). To ensure greater coordination between the city and regional levels, Karlstad set up a project office that centralises administrative tasks to coordinate the small ESF projects of all municipalities in the region to enable them to focus on project implementation.⁶⁷
- **Working through a network of intermediaries who can help incubate social innovation projects:**⁶⁸ The Polish ministry with responsibility for managing the ESF found that supporting social innovation and transnational cooperation using a horizontal approach was not conducive to building a social innovation ecosystem (it resulted in a lack of coordination and visibility of social innovation, and failed to bring about the necessary mainstreaming, promotion and upscaling of the many social innovations that had been developed through ESF funds). For this reason, the current programming period has adopted a more centralised approach, with responsibility for for coordinating and promoting social innovation sitting with the ministry. That said, the responsibility for providing direct support to social innovators is not carried out by the ministry. Instead, the OP relies on a network of incubators who in turn scout for ideas and

⁶⁵ EUROCIITIES (2018). Lessons learned from cities' experiences with the ESF in 2014-2017. Brussels. p. 16
Available online: http://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EUROCIITIES_report_on_ESF_and_cities_FINAL.pdf
[Accessed 13.12.18]

⁶⁶ *Ibid.* p. 16

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*

⁶⁸ Fondazione G. Brodolini. (2018). ESF Performance and Thematic Reports the ESF Support to Social Innovation, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available online: <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=738&langId=en&pubId=8107&furtherPubs=yes> [Accessed: 18/12/18]

provide support to social innovators by offering advice, counselling, and grant support (such as by undertaking financial/administrative work).

There are also examples of practices that indirectly support social innovation outcomes, such as:

- **Using technical assistance to support civil society development:** In Slovakia, the Office of the Plenipotentiary supported a one-year pilot project for the development of civil society with funding from the Operational Programme's technical assistance. While not done with the explicit objective of supporting social innovation, as the first ever case of an Operational Programme using technical assistance to cover the costs of non-state experts performing work on participation, partnership and transparency in ESIF monitoring and implementation,⁶⁹ this is an important ESF administrative innovation.
- **Intermediate body support for partnerships in Ireland⁷⁰:** In Ireland, the intermediate body Pobal (which is responsible for administering some ESF programmes) provides partnerships with developmental and technical assistance as well as guidance on organisational management and governance and specialist training around specific issues. This can include provision of information material on programme target groups, feedback on performance and strategies, or training inputs and discussions designed to address specific areas of challenge within the work. A liaison system in which Pobal officers service partnerships by attending board and management meetings also provides useful support to projects as they develop. In addition, events are organised as required at regional and national levels for key partnership staff and board members.

⁶⁹ Thematic Network on Partnership (2018). Initial findings and recommendations from European Code of Conduct on Partnership (ECCP) Review. Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/esf/transnationality/fledepot_download/564/1592 [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁷⁰ *Ibid.* p. 22

5. HOW FAR DOES ESF+ RESPOND TO THESE CHALLENGES?

In May 2018, the European Commission adopted proposals for a new Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) for 2021-2027. The Commission proposed that over this period, the new European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) will have a budget of €101.2 billion. The proposed ESF+ regulation directly addresses some - but not all - of the challenges that have so far made it difficult to use ESF for social innovation.

The EC proposes that ESF+ will merge five current EU funds: the European Social Fund, the Youth Employment Initiative (YEI), the Fund for European Aid to the Most Deprived (FEAD), the EU Programme for Employment and Social Innovation (EaSI), and the EU Health programme. The ESF+ Regulation will replace the current ESF, FEAD, EaSI and EU Health programme regulations and will have multiple legal bases.

These funds were merged with a view to making it easier for beneficiaries to access funding, help them combine different types of measures, and simplify the management of funding. As one of our consultees explained:

“Under the (in)direct management strand, the ESF+ will operate a series of improvements, including a sharper focus on disadvantaged groups and gender equality, greater budgetary flexibility and better integration between the current activities. The complementarities between social experimentation, analytical work, capacity-building, transnational activities and greater upscaling/deployment at national level will become clearer within the simplified ESF+ structure.”⁷¹

What are the main changes in how social innovation will be supported under the proposed ESF+, compared with the current regulation?

There are four key ways in which the ESF+ proposes to improve support for social innovation and experimentation. These include: more concrete indications of what ESF-supported social innovation looks like; greater clarity about how social innovation will be supported through different management modes of ESF+; co-financing to incentivise Member States to allocate shared management budget to social innovation; and more centralised support for transnational social innovation initiatives, through indirect management. These are outlined briefly here.

⁷¹ Background interview with EC official from DG EMPL.

01 New definitions of social innovation and social experimentation

Two big changes highlight how the European Commission is attempting to make social innovation easier to operationalise within ESF+. First, the new proposed regulation for ESF+ now offers a definition for social innovation - something the ESF regulation for the 2014 - 2020 stopped short of doing. The proposals published in *COM(2018) 382 final* state that:

'social innovations' mean activities that are social both as to their ends and their means and in particular those which relate to the development and implementation of new ideas (concerning products, services and models) that simultaneously meet social needs and create new social relationships or collaborations, thereby benefiting society and boosting its capacity to act⁷²

Further, with the incorporation of the EU Programme for Employment and Social Innovation (EaSI) into ESF+, a definition for social experimentation is also offered:

'social experimentations' mean policy interventions that offer an innovative response to social needs, implemented on a small scale and in conditions that enable their impact to be measured, prior to being implemented in other contexts or on a larger scale, if the results prove convincing.⁷³

02 A dedicated priority axis for social innovation

The draft ESF+ proposal suggests that Member States will be required to select social innovation as a priority axis - dedicating at least one priority to the implementation of a) social innovation and social experimentations, b) the upscaling of innovative approaches tested on a small scale (social experimentations) developed under the Employment and Social Innovation strand and other Union programmes - or both. This marks a significant reinforcing of social innovation as a priority of the ESF. In the 2014-2020 programming period Member States could prioritise social innovation as either an ESF Operational Programme or at a later stage during implementation in fields that correspond to the

⁷² Article 2: Definitions (16) Cited at: European Commission (2018). Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) {SEC(2018) 273 final} - {SWD(2018) 289 final} Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-may2018-european-social-fund-plus-regulation_en.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁷³ Article 2: Definitions (17) Cited at: European Commission (2018). Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) {SEC(2018) 273 final} - {SWD(2018) 289 final}

Member States' specific needs.

Furthermore, social innovation is given better visibility as a way to achieve different programme priorities, and in particular as a way to implement the European Pillar of Social Rights (which was proclaimed late in 2017 by the Parliament, the Council and the Commission at the Social Summit for Fair Jobs and Growth). To contribute to this policy objective of “A more social Europe - Implementing the European Pillar of Social Rights,”⁷⁴ innovative actions and approaches may be programmed under any of the ten specific objectives relating to employment, education, social inclusion and health. If accepted in the final ESF+ regulation, the promotion of social innovation as a dedicated priority of the ESF+ should make it easier to monitor, evaluate, and further knowledge and practices of social innovation supported within the framework of ESF+.

The ESF+ proposal also offers clarity around how social innovation supported under different management modes will interact, by introducing a double-track approach to clarify how social innovation initiatives and actions will be supported at the local, regional, national (through shared management), and transnational levels (through (in)direct management). Primarily, ESF+ will provide decentralised support to social innovation at member state and regional levels through shared management - where Member States are entrusted with implementing programmes at national level, and allocating funds to beneficiaries once Operational Programmes are negotiated between national authorities and the Commission. Implementation on the ground, through Operational Programmes, is managed by the relevant authorities in each country.⁷⁵ Member states will be able to allocate their ESF+ funds under shared management to ‘innovative actions’ including social innovation and social experimentation, novel partnerships between public authorities, the private sector and civil society, and upscaling of innovative concepts developed and tested at EU level (Union programmes).

Meanwhile, under indirect management, it will provide more centralised support for transnational social innovation initiatives, with the aim of transferring innovative solutions between Member States.⁷⁶ To

⁷⁴ Points (i) to (x) of Article 4(1) Cited at: European Commission (2018). Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) {SEC(2018) 273 final} - {SWD(2018) 289 final} Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-may2018-european-social-fund-plus-regulation_en.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁷⁵ Article 13, Innovative Actions Cited at: European Commission (2018). Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) {SEC(2018) 273 final} - {SWD(2018) 289 final} Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-may2018-european-social-fund-plus-regulation_en.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁷⁶ Article 23 i, Transnational Cooperation Cited at: European Commission (2018). Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) {SEC(2018) 273 final} - {SWD(2018) 289 final} Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-may2018-european-social-fund-plus-regulation_en.pdf

support innovative actions at local, regional or national levels through indirect management, the Commission has proposed a funding window under the Employment and Social Innovation strand to support transnational cooperation in designing and scaling-up social innovations.

The ESF+ proposals also create greater coherence between different levels of social innovation support. For example, an explicit connection is made between social innovation and Community-Led Local Development (CLLD), as well as other less formalised bottom-up or participatory approaches:

Member States shall support actions of social innovation and social experimentations, or strengthen bottom-up approaches based on partnerships involving public authorities, the private sector, and civil society such as the Local Action Groups designing and implementing Community-Led Local Development strategies.⁷⁷

In addition, it attempts to show how innovative actions supported through the shared management strand can be connected with the upscaling of innovative solutions through the EaSI strand, under direct and indirect management:

Member States may support the upscaling of innovative approaches tested on a small scale (social experimentations) developed under the Employment and Social Innovation strand and other Union programmes.⁷⁸

03 Co-financing to incentivise Member States to allocate shared management budget to social innovation

In the current programming period co-financing rates are divided into three funding categories based on Member States' GDP per head compared to the EU average. ESF co-financing rates vary between 50% and 85% (95% in exceptional cases) of the total project costs depending on the relative wealth of the region.

[european-social-fund-plus-regulation_en.pdf](#) [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁷⁷ Article 13 (Innovative actions) Cited at: European Commission (2018). Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) {SEC(2018) 273 final} - {SWD(2018) 289 final} Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-may2018-european-social-fund-plus-regulation_en.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁷⁸European Commission (2018). Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) {SEC(2018) 273 final} - {SWD(2018) 289 final} Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-may2018-european-social-fund-plus-regulation_en.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

Here we see some considerable changes in the ESF+ proposed regulation. The new proposals⁷⁹ aim to make it possible for member countries to allocate up to 5% of their national ESF+ allocation under shared management to Innovative Action priorities (Article 13 (4)) to take advantage of a more attractive co-financing rate, which has been increased to the maximum of 95%. While this will not increase the overall amounts for ESF, in some contexts this would see the current co-financing rate greatly increased, in particular for countries in the more developed region category, like Belgium or Ireland, which can currently avail of a co-financing rate of 50%. This creates a stronger financial incentive for Member States to make social innovation a dedicated priority of their Operational Programme, and to fund it by the maximum of 5% of their national allocation. Furthermore, if in theory if each member state dedicated 5% of the Operational Programme to social innovation, this would earmark approximately €5bn for social innovation priorities.

04 More centralised support for transnational social innovation initiatives through indirect management

The ESF+ proposals earmark €200 million for transnational cooperation to support the transfer of innovative solutions and learning across countries. Unlike in the current programming period, the EC proposes that this funding will be administered via indirect management (managed centrally by the EC, but with implementation being delegated to a managing authority for the entire programming period) rather than through 'shared management' with Member States. This is intended to reduce the administrative burden for national and subnational managing bodies, and to create a more coordinated approach between the European and Member State levels.

Stakeholders' reactions to ESF+

To what extent do the new proposals respond to the challenges identified in using ESF to support social innovation in the current programming period? We reviewed 11 documents posted by stakeholders, ESF managing authorities, intermediaries and beneficiaries that comment on the ESF+ proposals. These include feedback collected as part of the EC's public consultation (June to August 2018⁸⁰) as well as reports on relevant themes published subsequently by Eurocities⁸¹ and Social Services

⁷⁹ Article 13 (4), Innovative Actions. Cited at: European Commission (2018). Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) {SEC(2018) 273 final} - {SWD(2018) 289 final} Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-may2018-european-social-fund-plus-regulation_en.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁸⁰ Download from: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/initiatives/com-2018-382_en [Accessed 03.09.18]

⁸¹ http://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EUROCITIES_statement_ESF_final.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

Europe.⁸²

Our review found the following main reactions to the ESF+ proposal, and other areas for improvement which ESF stakeholders wanted to see underlined and supported to improve its effectiveness at achieving social innovation, innovative actions and social experimentation.

01 The concept of social innovation within the ESF+ framework may still need further clarification

The wide variety of social innovation projects and themes likely to be supported under ESF+ has led to calls for a better definition and awareness raising of social innovation. For example, **EuroHealthnet**⁸³ argue that the ESF+ proposal should “clarify what scope the ESF+ will give to supporting integrated work and implementation of good practices in areas of more preventative, structural, systemic and social innovations in public health.” They further note that, “the ESF+ intention to *mainstream effective preventative models... and solutions to contribute to innovative, efficient and sustainable health systems* is welcome. However, clearer assessments of how those solutions would reduce health and social inequalities, and go beyond individual approaches, are crucial. A recent systematic review of public health return on investment to health systems and societies demonstrates that public health interventions are highly cost-saving, by focusing on health promotion and prevention, wider determinants of health and change to legislative environments”.

02 A more flexible, impact-focused approaches to data collection is needed

In FEANTSA’s response to the ESF+,⁸⁴ the European NGO (whose mission is to tackle homelessness) noted that it “particularly welcomes the effort of the European Commission not to propose indicators demanding stringent identification requirements on the end beneficiaries.”⁸⁵ Indeed the need to

⁸² Social Services Europe (2018) The European Social Fund + (ESF+) proposal: Suggested Amendments. Available online: https://docs.wixstatic.com/ugd/9f45fc_597c9ed476644bbe9e2fa1aa3c5cca41.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁸³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/initiatives/com-2018-382/feedback/F13369_en?p_id=241718 [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁸⁴ <https://www.feantsa.org/download/feantsa-s-statement-on-the-esf+-erdf-and-cpf-2407184218445323643067453.pdf>

⁸⁵ Page 12, ESF+ regulation: “In order to simplify data collection and minimise the burden on participants and beneficiaries, the authorities will be enabled, as much as possible, to collect monitoring data from existing administrative registers. Sensitive data will not be collected directly from the participants and rely on registers or informed estimations.”

sometimes sacrifice such sensitive data in exchange for the opportunity to create a trusted client relationship has already been pursued in initiatives aimed at attracting hard to reach target groups, such as by Ohjaamo Finland.⁸⁶ However, FEANSTA went on to argue that some of the indicators currently being proposed are unsatisfactory as they do not provide any incentive for impact of the measure in terms of social inclusion or poverty alleviation. They suggest that several of the proposed output indicators of “monetary value” do not provide any information on the success of the programme. FEANTSA and partner organisations instead have called for indicators of a more impact-focused⁸⁷ and qualitative nature, linked to people’s living situation e.g. on the regularity or the support received, or the perceived impact in alleviating material deprivation.”⁸⁸

03 Civil society actors’ role in delivering ESF+ needs further clarification

Some feedback provided to ESF+ strongly underlines the need to better address the application of the partnership principle, particularly partnerships that involve civil society actors. In their joint response to the ESF+, the ONCE Foundation (Fundación ONCE), the Spanish Red Cross (Cruz Roja Española), Caritas Spain (Cáritas Española) and the Roma Secretariat Foundation (Fundación Secretariado Gitano) noted that in the post-2020 arrangement, “managing authorities [should be allowed to] appoint non-profit private organisations as intermediary bodies for the management and implementation of part of the Programmes; these organisations need to guarantee adequate capacity management; these organisations may receive the mandate from public authorities and have to be elected respecting the principles of transparency and non-discrimination. Intermediary bodies may manage operations directly or through final beneficiaries.” They argue this, citing that non-profit organisation can potentially play “a unique role in the management of EU Funds...therefore, the regulations should be explicit and foresee their capacity to be designated intermediary bodies.” They also note that the regulations should specify that intermediary bodies can either manage operations directly or through final beneficiaries.⁸⁹

⁸⁶ Stakeholder interview

⁸⁷ For instance, instead of “Total monetary value of distributed food and goods (meals, packages, etc)”, they instead propose that “Total number of units of distributed food and goods (meals, packages, etc).” is the preferred output indicator to ensure projects to tackle material deprivation are appropriately impact-focused. Cited from: <https://www.feantsa.org/download/feantsa-s-statement-on-the-esf+-erdf-and-cpf-2407184218445323643067453.pdf> p. 4. [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁸⁸ FEANSTA (2018) FEANTSA’S Position On The Future Of The European Social Fund Plus, European Regional And Development Fund And Common Provision Framework. Available online: <https://www.feantsa.org/download/feantsa-s-statement-on-the-esf+-erdf-and-cpf-2407184218445323643067453.pdf> [Accessed 13.12.18]

⁸⁹ Download at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/initiatives/com-2018-382/feedback/F12874_en?p_id=241718 [Accessed 13.12.18]

04 There is a need for more emphasis on establishing mechanisms to scale up and transfer social innovation approaches between regions

EURoma⁹⁰ proposes the following improvements to the ESF+ Regulation proposal: “[The ESF+ should offer] [c]learer emphasis on the need to establish mechanisms to scale up and give continuity to proven-positive innovative initiatives. Further indications in this regard should be included to assure the scaling up of practices that prove to be efficient, since otherwise opportunities may be lost despite positive intentions. This is of particular interest for complex cases referred to social inclusion and discrimination measures (p. 5)”.

⁹⁰ Download at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/initiatives/com-2018-382/feedback/F13578_en?p_id=241718 [Accessed 13.12.18]

05 ESF+ could include an objective on piloting place-based social innovation

The Eurocities response to the ESF+⁹¹ proposal strongly recommends cities as the best level for experimentation with social innovation before mainstreaming, and points out that unless representatives from local level are committed to social innovation goals, there is likely to be a mismatch between policy intentions and implementation. An objective focused on piloting place-based social innovation could place a specific emphasis on integrated approaches to combine people-based interventions with a place-based focus. For this reason, EUROCITIES argue for a better definition of ‘partnership’ under Article 8 by adding a specific reference to urban and local authorities and calling for their meaningful involvement in all phases of the programming, and the reintroduction of a provision to encourage global grants as a form of involving ‘partners’ (cities) in the implementation of operational programmes (article 6.1 of current ESF regulation).⁹² In tandem with this, effective initiatives developed under the ERDF’s European Territorial Cooperation – such as those led by URBACT – or ‘reciprocity contracts’ could be rolled out in the next programming period to help overcome regional disparities, such as the urban/rural divide.

06 Clarity needed to explain proposed change to manage transnational cooperation indirect management

The proposed change to have transnational cooperation managed by indirect rather than shared management in 2021-2027 has been met with mixed responses. While our consultees recognised the benefits of transnational cooperation and spoke of a desire for more intensive and well resourced transnational learning networks, the specific proposals for transnational cooperation in the ESF+ were not all well received. For instance, some of the experts consulted for this study,⁹³ noted that this shift to indirect management had been met with resistance by certain members of the European Council. The policy experts we consulted argued this change was proposed to respond to a key insight from the Commission’s ESF+ consultations that under the shared management system, coordinated transnational calls were found to be very labour intensive for national or regional authorities to manage. Social innovation and social experimentation (especially when linked to transnational cooperation to support the transfer of and scaling of innovative solutions across Europe) can also be overlooked as they often sit outside Member States’ national or regional policy priorities. Therefore, the motivation for going back to (in)direct management of transnational cooperation at EU level is to reduce the

⁹¹ EUROCITIES (2018). A smart investment in people: EUROCITIES position on ESF+ Available online: http://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EUROCITIES_statement_ESF_final.pdf [Accessed: 18/12/18]

⁹² Cited at: EUROCITIES (2018) A smart investment in people: EUROCITIES position on ESF+ Available online: http://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EUROCITIES_statement_ESF_final.pdf [Accessed: 18/12/18]

⁹³ Expert interviews and SIC policy roundtable.

administrative burden for national and subnational managing bodies, and through more attractive co-financing rates, ensure the benefits of transnational cooperation are made more visible within ESF+.

Other stakeholders have reacted to the ESF+ regulation's transnational cooperation proposals not because of the shift in management modes, but because of a desire to open the kinds of stakeholders who can participate in and lead transnational innovative actions. On this topic, EURO CITIES have argued that "Transnational cooperation should not be limited to the innovations upscaled by Member States but should be extended to city-to-city piloting of tested innovations to help transfer successful innovations."⁹⁴

⁹⁴ EURO CITIES (2018). A smart investment in people: EURO CITIES position on ESF+ Available online: http://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EUROCITIES_statement_ESF_final.pdf [Accessed: 18/12/18]

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

A key finding of this report is that the rationale for using the ESF to support social innovation is not clearly articulated, and needs to be more explicit. In particular, the concept and goals of social innovation and social experimentation are not well understood by important ESF stakeholders, particularly in the context of delivering a more social Europe. Our consultations suggest that this may be one of the unintended consequences of ‘mainstreaming’ social innovation in the current programming period.⁹⁵

Our quantitative data analysis suggests that in the current programming period, €2.84 billion has been allocated to social innovation; this represents around 3% of the total ESF budget. While this is a considerable volume of activity, it is a lower proportion than was achieved in the 2000-2006 programming period, when Member States were required to allocate 5% of their ESF budgets to the EQUAL Community Initiative. The majority of ESF-funded social innovation activity is concentrated in a relatively small number of countries.

Related to this point, our research has found that three major but related barriers are hindering the potential of ESF-supported social innovation. First, limited awareness and understanding amongst political leaders and public managers means that social innovation often lacks political and institutional buy-in. This makes it harder to prioritise social innovation actions at macro or micro levels, form high-level partnerships, or to update relevant national policies or legislation. In practice, ESF managing authorities may operate at a remove from other government agencies, and consequently there can be disconnect between their activities and policies and those led by other public agencies and leaders.

Second, a widespread lack of ‘internal’ innovation capacity amongst key ESF bodies⁹⁶ means that innovative actions are viewed as being more difficult to set up and manage when compared with conventional ESF project calls.⁹⁷ While ESF managing bodies are tasked with designing social innovation project calls and establishing support mechanisms, we found that they often lack the expertise needed to do this effectively.⁹⁸

⁹⁵ European Commission official, SIC online roundtable, October 2018.

⁹⁶ Here we are referring to national, regional or local governments, managing authorities, civil society and social economy organisations, Local Action Groups, and grassroots and community initiatives.

⁹⁷ Expert interview

⁹⁸ Discussion point mentioned during SIC’s policy roundtable, Optimising the ESF+ for Social Innovation, October 12th 2018.

Finally, ESF beneficiaries and ‘external stakeholders’ often lack the competencies needed to effectively prepare, design, implement, evaluate and sustain innovative actions. Project beneficiaries looking to access management, professional support and training related to these specific needs find it difficult to do so since the cost of such training and support is not eligible for reimbursement.

While there are some examples of managing authorities who are creatively using the framework of the ESF to support social innovation and social experimentation, these examples of administrative experiments are not being done at scale. Building on our findings, below we present a number of proposals which have the potential to greatly improve the ESF+’s effectiveness as an instrument that can catalyse social innovation.

Recommendations

At the time of writing, negotiations are well underway on the new ESF+ proposal, and responses to the proposed regulation have been drafted and discussed by the European Economic and Social Committee,⁹⁹ the Committee of the Regions,¹⁰⁰ and European Parliament’s Committee for Employment and Social Affairs have prepared a report on the future regulation.¹⁰¹

Our analysis suggests that some additional regulatory proposals and amendments could be incorporated into the future ESF+ regulation, if it is to be used to better support social innovation.

However, our analysis also shows that difficulties in using ESF for social innovation arise not only from the regulation, but also from challenges relating to implementation, such as a lack of knowledge and capacity among managing authorities. We therefore make several proposals as to how managing authorities could be better supported to promote social innovation as a way of achieving the goals of ESF+.

We recommend that:

01 The ESF+ regulation should require Member States to allocate a minimum

⁹⁹ European Economic and Social Committee (2018) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) [COM(2018) 382 final – 2018/0206 (COD)] (Adopted 17/10/18)

Available online: <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/our-work/opinions-information-reports/opinions/european-social-fund> [Accessed: 18.12.18]

¹⁰⁰ Available online: <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/sides/getDoc.do?type=COMPARL&reference=PE-626.720&format=PDF&language=EN&secondRef=01> [Accessed: 22.11.18]

¹⁰¹ <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-new-boost-for-jobs-growth-and-investment/file-mff-esf> [Accessed: 22.11.18]

of 5% of their national ESF budget to support innovative actions (as outlined in Article 13).

The introduction of a minimum allocation of the national ESF+ contribution to social innovation will refocus national OPs on social innovation as a way to achieve policy objectives, would address potential bottlenecks in designing or implementing innovative actions under shared management, and will give greater recognition to the role and activities of grassroots and civil society initiatives and organisations.

The positive experience of employing minimum allocations under social innovation-related priorities in current ERDF and EAFRD provides a clear precedent and justification for this:

- Articles 7 and 8 of the ERDF Regulation states that at least 5% of ERDF resources allocated at national level under the investment for growth and jobs goal shall be ring-fenced to support integrated sustainable urban development strategies (or ‘urban innovative actions’).^{102,103}
- The EAFRD regulation requires that Member States or regions must make a 5% minimum allocation of their funds to rural development priorities connected to LEADER (Community-Led Local Development).¹⁰⁴

Both examples specify the allocation of the Community contribution to these priorities in quantitative terms (“at least 5%”). The ESF contribution to the EQUAL social innovation programme was also 5%.

Some of our consultees have indicated that in the current programming period (2014-2020), the optional nature of social innovation as an ESF priority has contributed to a lessening of its impact and visibility.¹⁰⁵ For this reason, the protection of a dedicated social innovation priority axis is important for two reasons in particular: 1) it creates a stronger incentive for more Member States and managing authorities to explore how they can create better outcomes through ESF-supported social innovation; and 2) it helps facilitate increased policy learning about the social innovation field supported by ESF, by making it easier to detect, monitor and validate social innovations incubated through the programme.

02 The European Commission, Member States and key ESF implementing bodies should invite wider stakeholder involvement in defining and co-delivering ESF+ priorities.

¹⁰² Available online: http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/activity/urban/urban_innovative_actions.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

¹⁰³ Available online:

http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docgener/informat/2014/guidance_sustainable_urban_development_en.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

¹⁰⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/rural-development-2014-2020_en [Accessed 22.11.18]

¹⁰⁵ Participant SIC online roundtable: How can the ESF+ be optimised for social innovation? October 12th, 2018.

Partnership is both an important feature of ESF-supported social innovation¹⁰⁶ and a central principle of the ESF. Better partnerships therefore have the potential to unleash better ESF-supported social innovation that is more closely aligned with target users real needs. Communities, end users, social innovation practitioners, civil society organisations, social partners and local/regional actors should be more systematically involved in defining priorities and co-delivering activities to address them. Clear consideration should be given to how to encourage partnerships (building on the ECCP and Community-Led Local Development principles and approaches) that move beyond compliance to meaningful multi-stakeholder collaboration¹⁰⁷ between a wider set of actors and across all stages of the programme lifecycle. Particular efforts should be made to ensure local voices are incorporated in programme decision-making and governance through place-based, bottom-up and participative approaches such as CLLD and [Talanoa Dialogue](#)¹⁰⁸ when being rolled out in the next programming period. This can be achieved by:

- **Raising awareness, learning and exchange about the European Code of Conduct on Partnership to ensure that inclusive, meaningful partnerships are at the heart of defining ESF+ priorities through Partnership Agreements, Operational Programmes and Monitoring Committees.** Other tried and tested methods such as European Territorial Cooperation initiatives – like those led by URBACT – or ‘reciprocity contracts’ for overcoming the urban/rural divide, European Social Dialogue to promote gender equality, and the Talanoa Dialogue for climate change should be highlighted and rolled out when designing approaches to implement the objectives of the Sustainable Development Goals and European Pillar of Social Rights.
- **Ensuring training and technical assistance can be used by support more inclusive partnerships.** Taking the precedent established in Latvia, Member States should ensure that partnership training is made available to public administration agencies, NGOs and other stakeholders who wish to increase their knowledge and expertise on implementation of the

¹⁰⁶ SIC’s 2017 State of the Union policy report found that all the examples of employment-related social innovation included cross-sector collaboration between partners such as local and national governments, funding bodies, civil society organisations and in certain cases, research institutions or end-users. See more at: N. Ahmed et al. (2017) D5.6: Annual State of the Union Report – Part 2: How is EU employment policy driving social innovation? p. 64. https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/how_is_eu_employment_policy_driving_social_innovation.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

¹⁰⁷ A review of the European Code of Conduct on Partnership (ECCP) carried out by the ESF Partnerships Transnational Network finds that MAs need to make more efforts to go beyond compliance at the institutional level when putting the principle into practice. Source: Thematic Network on Partnership (2018) Initial findings and recommendations from European Code of Conduct on Partnership (ECCP) Review. https://ec.europa.eu/esf/transnationality/fledepot_download/564/1592 [Accessed 13.12.18]

¹⁰⁸ See more at: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/newsroom/events/2018/06/eu-for-talanoa [Accessed 18/12/18]

partnership principle in ESF+ (and ESIF) programmes and projects.¹⁰⁹ Specific capacity-building training is required to meet the following recognised needs: effective selection for Monitoring Committees and their working practices; ensuring ongoing involvement of stakeholders; managing the review and assessment of ongoing projects; and designing effective mechanisms for exchange and learning between the different stakeholders. Co-production approaches should be promoted as a means to make the ESF+ more inclusive, to activate citizen participation, create tailored service options for different end users and, in so doing, assist in deepening the quality of implementation of the partnership and Community-Led Local Development principles.¹¹⁰

- **Broadening the focus of the ESF+ regulation to recognise the key role that city, regional and local stakeholders can play as partners and call for their meaningful involvement in all phases of programming.** In the 2014-2020 period, the ESF explicitly recognised the involvement of local and regional authorities delivering “efficient and effective implementation of actions supported by the ESF”. When involved in co-delivering ESF initiatives, city, regional and local authorities can act as an important catalyst for social innovation - piloting social innovations, and mainstreaming good practices in regular service provision to improve public services.¹¹¹ The article on partnership specifically refers to social partners and civil society; it fails to mention the role that city, local and regional authorities can play “who are the closest to citizens and know their needs best”.¹¹²

03 The European Commission and Member States should create a network of national competence centres to improve the support environment for ESF-supported social innovation.

SIC’s policy opinion on the ESF+ proposal¹¹³ is that if the EaSI strand is to deliver better social experimentation outcomes on the ground, it needs to give greater strategic focus to practical support and capacity-building actions that ensure consistency, coherence and synergy of EU support for social

¹⁰⁹ The training rolled out in Latvia was undertaken as part of the ‘Provision of training services to institutions of Latvia involved in the management of the European Union Funds’ scheme, was developed as a series of lectures, discussions, workshops, interactive group and individual exercises, as well as analyses of relevant case studies and sessions aimed at exchange of experiences. See: Thematic Network on Partnership (2018) Initial findings and recommendations from European Code of Conduct on Partnership (ECCP) Review. Available online:

https://ec.europa.eu/esf/transnationality/filedepot_download/564/1592 [Accessed 13.12.18]

¹¹⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/esf/transnationality/filedepot_download/1145/1723 [Accessed 13.12.18]

¹¹¹ http://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EUROCITIES_report_on_ESF_and_cities_FINAL.pdf [Accessed 13.12.18]

¹¹² http://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EUROCITIES_statement_ESF_final.pdf pp. 1-2. [Accessed 13.12.18]

¹¹³ Social Innovation Community (2018). European Social Fund Plus (ESF+): Social Innovation as a Path to a Sustainable, Resilient and Inclusive Europe: A statement from the Social Innovation Community

experimentation, CLLD actions, social innovation and transnational scaling of innovative solutions. This acknowledges that EaSI's total budget is likely to drop from €919 million (in 2013 prices) to €761 million (in current prices).

To strengthen the impact and relevance of the EaSI's critical social experimentation objectives, a network of national competence centres should be set up across the EU-27. Examples of the activities the centres should support include:

- **Developing training and capacity-building support for public leaders and officials (in partnership with training and education providers and schools of government)** to deepen awareness on the benefits, characteristics and potential bottlenecks for ESF+-supported social innovation through targeted meetings and workshops that support the development of a future pipeline programmes, projects and pilot actions with social innovation principles at their core.
- **Offering managing bodies management support and a platform for learning and practice exchange** to design better social innovation project calls that reflect beneficiaries' needs (especially smaller social actors') at each phase of the project life cycle.
- **Providing capacity-building supports for project promoters and stakeholders (especially smaller social and civil society actors)** to increase access to the specialist professional skills and supports they need for their social innovation projects to be effectively set up or scaled.
- **Developing practical guidance, support and technical assistance** built on research, learning and practice for the design, preparation, implementation, evaluation, adaptation or replication of innovative actions.
- **Creating links to national policy in Member States**, to create more opportunities for initiatives funded through ESF+ to become mainstreamed, and to help ensure that learning is transferred between ESF+ initiatives and national policy agendas.

04 The European Commission should create a new European Observatory of Social Innovation Policy¹¹⁴ to mainstream and monitor the performance of cross-cutting social innovation policy approaches.

Currently there is no institutionalised support to detect and validate ESF-supported social innovations in a long-term and sustained way, which makes it difficult to easily assess the full extent of ESF-supported social innovation activity. An Observatory would provide long-term monitoring functions in priority themes relevant to the ESF+, and could make links with other policy fields and funds to promote more integrated and multi-funded social innovation policy approaches. It would support transnational policy learning and transfer by identifying high-potential social innovations and emerging social innovation

¹¹⁴ The concept for a European Observatory of Social Innovation Policy was included in SIC's Lisbon Declaration. See more at: Social Innovation Community (2018) The Lisbon Declaration - Social Innovation As A Path to A Sustainable, Resilient and Inclusive Europe Available online: https://www.siceurope.eu/sites/default/files/field/attachment/the_lisbon_social_innovation_declaration15.10.0.pdf

fields, trends and technologies across the EU-27, especially those that can support implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals and European Pillar of Social Rights.

By complementing the actions of the Employment and Social Innovation strand, the Observatory would help deepen the relevance and impact of social experimentation by:

- Boosting the impact of social experimentation through hands-on and demand-led support for relevant stakeholders¹¹⁵ in the design and comparative evaluation of social innovations.
- Identifying and validating high-potential social innovations, good practices and scalable solutions, which can be incorporated into national policy reform packages or replicated and scaled transnationally, through transnational learning networks.
- Designing transnational learning exercises between relevant managing bodies and projects to help adapt, replicate or scale promising social innovation pilots, experiments and programmes from elsewhere.

05 The European Commission should make it possible for managing bodies and others to experiment with rules and regulations, to help ensure they are proportionate and flexible to support social innovation.

At a 'centralised' level, the ESF+ should continue to steer the programme focus from actions and expenses to results and output. Experiments such as those being carried out with piloting ESF Joint Action Plans present an important opportunity to explore how the administrative burden of the programme can be reduced, and can give more insight into the impact and cost effectiveness of actions. This should continue in the next programming period. Some additional ways the regulation could be experimented with include the following:

- **Setting up (and agreeing with the EC) realistic 'light' targets in the Operational Programmes for social innovation-specific priorities.** To support the kinds of innovations that it is envisaged Article 13 will catalyse, the EC should work with Member States, practitioners, and other relevant ESF stakeholders to devise flexible, proportionate targets in the OPs related to social innovation. These would have different application procedures and eligibility criteria and use flat rates and simplified access procedures to reduce the system of controls and speed up financing. Audit rules should be relaxed somewhat for social innovation and social experimentation actions so that they can support creativity and purposeful risk-taking.
- **Creating ESF+ Social Innovation Sandboxes to support administrative experimentation.** These would be new mechanisms set up to create a controlled environment where standard

¹¹⁵ As with the PROGRESS axis of EaSI currently, support should be made open to all public and/or private bodies, actors and institutions (including international organisations) who have an interest in using the ESF to support social experimentation (linked to the achievement of its policy objectives).

rules and regulations can be relaxed so that managing bodies can prototype and test new regulatory alternatives that aim to address common social innovation barriers before implementation. Managing authorities should be able to dedicate up to 10% of ESF+ (and ERDF) funding to experimental projects, with rules around eligibility and monitoring significantly relaxed. A proportion of the Sandbox activities would focus on bringing ESF+ management bodies, programme practitioners and beneficiaries together to understand common regulatory barriers and prototype and test proposed alternatives before implementation. Sandbox activities would focus on experimenting with new ways of working and strategies that could help redesign the complexity of the ESIF system and better support beneficiaries (such as advancing 50 - 80% funding for small organisations which do not have adequate financial resources to deal with delays in payments), with a view to validating and mainstreaming what works within the wider system.

- **At an Operational Programme level, creating tailored and responsive monitoring, evaluation and reporting arrangements** where indicators, milestones and targets are defined according to the stages or aims of social innovation or social experimentation projects. There needs to be some flexibility to respond to the specific goals and aims of individual projects: for instance, very early-stage pilots should be evaluated using less rigid criteria than later-stage transfer or upscaling actions (of an already validated social innovation, where expected results are better known). When developing such performance frameworks, inspiration could be drawn from the Standards of Evidence framework,¹¹⁶ which considers the ‘maturity’ of an initiative.

¹¹⁶ Mulgan, G., & Puttick, R. (2013). Making Evidence Useful. London: Nesta. Available online: https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/making_evidence_useful.pdf [Accessed: 18/12/18]

7. APPENDIX: LIST OF CONSULTEES

Person	Role and Organisation
Andrea Leruste	Deputy head of unit ESF, DG Employment and Social Inclusion, European Commission
Loris Servillo	UCL, Lead Author of the EC-commissioned “CLLD under ERDF/ESF in the EU: A stock-taking of its implementation”
Costanza Pagnini	Economist, project manager at Fondazione Giacomo Brodolini
Nenad Maljkovic	ESF project beneficiary, Milo Za Drago (HR)
Aleksandra Kowalska	AEIDL, Member of the Platform for Transnational Cooperation for the European Social Fund (BE)
Felipe Almeida	Portugal Social Innovation (PT)
Antonio Miguel	ESF project beneficiary, Maze Impact (PT)
Vitor Nogueira	ESF Unit, DG Employment and Social Inclusion, European Commission
Brikena Xhomaqi	Director, Lifelong Learning Platform (EU-BE)
Marija Babovic	Chair of European Anti Poverty Network's (EAPN) Social Innovation Task Force, Co-Chair of EAPN's EU Inclusion Strategies Group, (EU)
Gerhard Braunling	Independent Policy Adviser - Social Innovation and European Social Fund
Annet Bek	ESF Managing Authority (NL)
Gorazd Jenko	Government Office for Development and European Cohesion Policy (SI)

Simona Hočeva	ESF managing authority (SI)
Vladimir Kvaca	Independent consultant, former Director of Partnership Agreement, Evaluation and Strategy department, Ministry of Regional Development (CZ)
Zulfiqar Ahmed	Global Director, Network Programmes, Impact Hub Network (EU)